

TURAMYIMANA FAUSTIN

CHUK

A&E dept

NUTRITION EVALUATION IN CLITICALLY ILL PATIENTS AT ACCIDENT EMERGENCY AT CHUK, QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT

BACKGROUND: Malnutrition is commonly encountered in hospitalized critically ill patients and it is often overlooked, poorly treated and largely contributes to poor outcomes and increased mortality(1)(2). Due to high stress and/or severe injury, these critically ill patients rapidly break their energy reserve and become subject to malnutrition unless adequate nutrition is provided(3)(4). There are limited data on outcome associated to poor nutrition for critically ill patient in sub-Saharan Africa, but there are large proportion of hospital acquired malnutrition in Sub-Saharan Africa (5). In Rwanda, at University Teaching Hospital of Kigali (CHUK), the emergency department is the first to receive all medical, surgical and accidental emergencies including critically ill patients. Those critically patients may spend several days, even weeks, before physical admission in their respective departments. During their stay in the ED, they benefit from different types of management which ideally includes nutrition. This inspired this quality improvement project designed to evaluate feeding these patients, identify gaps of feeding them, and provide suggestions and/or possible solutions to optimize feeding those patients.

METHODS: This study was a prospective evaluation of nutrition of critically ill patients in the CHUK emergency department. The study was completed over one month, with data collected weekly, the same day of Thursday between 25th July, 2022 to 21st August, 2022. Patients records of nutrition (amount food given, qualities food given (e.g.: protein rich diet, calories rich diet, fruits, vegetables) were collected and analyzed in excel. Inclusion criteria were based on severity of their conditions and need of nutrition support. Therefore, patients included in the study were red and orange (according to triage system, red patients are very sick/unstable patients who need immediately action and orange patients are sick patients who can deteriorate any time and become a red patient) admitted in the ED. Excluded patients were patients who were admitted the same day of data collection, patients who were put on nil per oral for different reasons and patients who were able to adequately to feed themselves.

RESULTS: A total of 27 patients were included in the study, 37 patients were evaluated with 10 patients excluded. Twelve patients (44%) were intubated and exclusively fed through nasogastric tube. One of twelve intubated patients (8 % of all intubated patients) had all records of nutrition including documented nutritional visit, amount of food, quality, times of administration, and nursing signature. Only four of intubated patients (33%) had benefited from a nutritionist visit and a prescription of diet. Five of total 27 patients (14.8%) were being fed without nutritionist visits. Nutrition quantity and quality of food administered were

specified on 7 patients (26%) and 11 patients (40.7%) respectively. And frequency of feeding was specified in 5 patients (18.5%) and 5 had had skipped diets at several occasions. Seventeen patients (62%) were not fed at all. Documented nutrition quantity and quality was recorded in 4 patients and feeding records were not signed by nurses in 7 patients (25.9%). And lastly, nutritional record sheets were not available in 12 patient's files (44.4%).

CONCLUSION: A regular nutritionist visit and clear prescription, physician and nursing team's implication and nutrition record documentation are keys to proper patient nutrition and expected outcome.

Participants

RESIDENT	TURAMYIMANA FAUSTIN
REVIEWER	DESTRY
SUPERVISOR	TWAGIRUMUKIZA FRANCOIS REGIS
MEMBERS OF IMPROVEMENT TEAM	Physician, residents, nurses, nutritionists

PROJECT DETAILS

TITLE OF THE PROJCT	EVALUATION OF NUTRITION IN CRITICALLY ILL PATIEINT AT CHUK EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT
START DATE	JUNE 2022
END DATE	NOVEMBER 2022
AIM OF THE PROJECT	Efficient feeding in critically ill patient
CONTEXT	Most patients are inadequately fed or nutrition left behind priority
Why is the project important?	There is need of nutrition improvement and need of gaps in nutrition in patients who cannot feed themselves. Together with other parts of patient's treatment, appropriate nutrition will bring about prompt desired patient outcome.
What will be changed and how will this change be implemented	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To prioritize nutrition in very ill patients in clear way 2. Nutrition sheet and prescription sheet, fluid sheets could be made in one sheet 3. Feeding of very ill patient could be done by only nursing team 4. Feeding could be done in appropriate frequency, quality, quantity in terms of calories, proteins, minerals, carbohydrates 5. Feeding once done, should be documented,

	when, how, quantity and quality
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Measures

Outcomes measures	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Nurses sensitization/mobilization for prioritizing feeding patient2. Nutrition sheet to be updated3. Regular evaluation of indices of patient nutrition's and documentation4. Nutritionist involvement
Process measures	Weekly evaluations of implementation progress
Balancing measures	Looking for barriers to patients feeding and nutrition and fix them

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